

THE ADVANTAGES OF USING GAMES IN TEACHING VOCABULARY (AT HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS)

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Annotation: This article gives vivid information about the pros sides of using games in teaching new vocabulary at higher educational institutions. Not only several pros sides of the usage of games in teaching vocabulary, but also a great number of acute examples and explanations of some games are given in this paperwork that helps learners acquire the new vocabulary easily.

Keywords: Advantages, games, tips, new vocabulary, higher educational institutions, acquisition of vocabulary.

Аннотация: В данной статье дается наглядная информация о плюсах использования игр в обучении новой лексике в высших учебных заведениях. В этом документе приведены не только несколько положительных сторон использования игр при обучении словарному запасу, но и большое количество ярких примеров и пояснений к некоторым играм, что помогает учащимся легко осваивать новый словарный запас.

Ключевые слова: Преимущества, игры, подсказки, новая лексика, высшие учебные заведения, приобретение словарного запаса.

In contemporary life using games for teaching vocabulary is becoming more popular activity day by day. Actually, understanding the importance of positive sides of utilizing games is essential at higher educational institutions. There are a great number of positive sides of using games in teaching new words. Generally, when teachers use some games so as to teach new vocabulary, they can not only encourage, entertain but also promote fluency through games while teaching new words. There a great number of pros sides of using games while teaching vocabulary.

Relaxing learning atmosphere When games are used for acquiring new words, student feel soothing learning atmosphere that inspire them to go ahead. Having finished learning and practicing vocabulary, learners have a chance to use them without stress. While acquiring new vocabulary, the most important thing in the student's mind is winning a game not learning new words. At this period learners learn everything unconsciously.

Saving time in real life, games stand as the crucial tool of the language learning process. While games are used by teachers, we can come across saving time

activities. For example, on behalf of teachers, we know that there is an abundance of chores that they must do during teaching learners. That's why they are not able to manage their time correctly. When they use games, they have never come across with above-mentioned problem. Because, instead of asking one by one, you can ask by dividing them into some groups. For example, last lesson you gave students 20 synonyms as a home task, today you will ask them by dividing them into 2 groups. With the help of this game, teachers can evaluate all learners.

Learning from each other The majority of students are too quick to answer and almost all answers which they submit are correct. But there are some language learners that are a bit passive compared to their peers. However, they can acquire some new words from their peers when they are answering. There is one advertisement porter game that is popular in teaching vocabulary. Just after having learned some words regarding tourism or other themes, students work in four or five small groups and the object of this game is for students should demonstrate a poster with short sentences using the words which they have learned recently.

Actually, students said that through this game they enrich their vocabulary because of listening to their groupmates.

Quickness Thanks to games that are created to make ease the process of learning new words, learning new words is becoming a quick process. When students learn new words with groups through some games and competitions, they learn them in fast way. That means that the speed of learning is very high when games are used to teach new words.

Quantity After having talked with several learners, it is observed that the rate of learning new words is very high when games are used to teach vocabulary sources. As games are used to teach new words, learners learn much because of being interested in games. During this period acquisition of new words will be high and learners learn much at this time.

Improves memory During playing some word games, learners work on their brains as well. They must repeat some words, definitions, and spelling after each other. In order to prepare for games they may also study and learn new terms. That all help them to improve their memory also.

Promotion to self-improving competition Some word games could be highly competitive and even frustrating for language learners. However, compared to being against an opponent. Players are fighting against themselves. To succeed, they must keep learning and improving their language learning. They must

increase their vocabulary source as much as possible. Thus, to succeed in something learners should work on themselves. They learn all through games of course.

Conclusion: The last but not least, we should keep in our mind that learning is too complex a process, but there are some ways, in order to make it easy as possible. Using games is so essential. Additionally, we should keep in our mind the pros sides of using games while teaching new terms even at higher institutions that are vital in the teaching process.

References:

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